

In a broad sense, engineering is the use of scientific principles and innovation to design and build a wide range of facilities. Engineering involves the use of scientific innovations in solving real applied problems, which contributes to the development of the skills of an inventor and innovator among specialists.

Thus, the STEM approach offers, first of all, the systematic introduction of a new, engineering and technological aspect of education into the school based on a digital platform.

In traditional education, the subjects of the NMC: physics, mathematics, chemistry, biology, and computer science are studied separately, their content does not intersect with each other in any way, leaving scattered pieces of information in the student's memory. The subject area "Technology" allows you to build logical connections between these disciplines, look at the world around you globally, and learn the patterns more deeply.

Thus, STEM education involves: 1) the transition from a purely fundamental approach to studying the subjects of the STEM to studying them in the context

of the practical application of scientific knowledge in solving applied problems from real life; 2) strengthening the applied, practical and laboratory-experimental components of the content of the subjects of the NMC; 3) Determining the content of the subject "Technology" by integrating the content of the subjects of the NMC, informatics and robotics in order to gradually master various technologies, form engineering and technological skills; 4) The use of robotics in the laboratory and experimental work of subjects of the NMC.

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PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR CORRECTING NEGATIVE MANIFESTATIONS IN 3-YEAR-OLD CHILDREN IN PRESCHOOLS

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Abstract

The early age is an important and challenging stage of the development of a person. The problem of overcoming negative manifestations during a three-year-old crisis seems to be especially relevant, because at this stage the consciousness and social position of the child are being developed. Lack of peculiar conditions for upbringing and communication with a child, those that are based on age-specific features and contributing to the smooth course of the restructuring the mentality, can lead to irreversible consequences that have an impact on personality development in the future.

The analysis of the proposed methods of overcoming the negative manifestations of the 3-year-old crisis showed that they do not provide thorough characteristics of the pedagogical conditions crucial for the evolutionary development of the personality at this age stage. The purpose of the study is to identify pedagogical conditions that contribute to overcoming negative manifestations in the behavior of three-year-old children in a preschool educational institution. Research methods: theoretical analysis of literature, practical experience analysis, generalization of empirically obtained data, observation, interview, experiment, mathematical methods of data processing.

Keywords: early age, 3-year-old behavior crisis, negative manifestations, preschool educational institution.

Introduction. The early age is an important and challenging stage of the development of a person. The problem of overcoming negative manifestations during a three-year-old crisis seems to be especially relevant, because at this stage the consciousness and social position of the child are being developed. Lack of peculiar conditions for upbringing and communication with a child, those that are based on age-specific features and contributing to the smooth course of the restructuring the mentality, can lead to irreversible consequences that

have an impact on personality development in the future.

Various options for overcoming the crisis in 3-year-olds have been considered by domestic and international educators and psychologists, such as foreign teachers and psychologists: L.S. Vygotsky, A.N. Leontiev, L. I. Bozhovich, D.B. Elkonin, E. Erickson, G. Bronson, S. Wolf, T.V. Guskova, M.G. Elagina, T.E. Dragunova, M.I. Lisina, A. Clarke, N.A. Menchinskaya, V.S. Mukhina, J. Rusek, L. White, E.

Kehler. Among the conditions for the successful overcoming the crisis, they claim taking into account the new needs of the child, respect of the personality of the child and a tactful attitude towards him/her, especially in emotionally stressful situations, rejecting the desire to tame the child, providing him/her with opportunities to reasonably demonstrate their independence, avoiding the potentially stressful situations for the child that could lead to aggravation of relationships with others, et al.

However, in most cases, recommendations on how to achieve this are of a general nature and relate to raising a child in a family. The analysis of the proposed methods of overcoming the negative manifestations of the 3-year-old crisis showed that they do not provide thorough characteristics of the pedagogical conditions crucial for the evolutionary development of the personality at this age stage. They do not present a holistic picture of the possible pedagogical influence on the child, the role of the preschool educator and the possibilities of the preschool educational organization in overcoming this crisis are not considered, although a significant number of toddlers are currently attending preschools. Therefore, it became necessary to consider the possibilities of reducing the negative symptoms of the 3-year-old behavior crisis from a pedagogical point of view.

The **aim** of the study is to identify pedagogical conditions that contribute to overcoming negative manifestations in the 3-year-old behavior crisis in a preschool educational institution. **The objectives of the study:** to diagnose the symptoms and frequency of manifestations of symptoms of the 3-year-old behavior crisis, to identify the direction and stability of negative manifestations of children during their stay in a preschool institution, to determine pedagogical conditions that contribute to overcoming negative manifestations of 3-year-old children's behavior.

Theoretical background. It was E. Kohler who first gave a meaningful description of the 3-year-old behavior crisis, highlighting its symptoms - negativism, stubbornness, obstinacy, self-will, devaluation of adults, protest-rebellion, and inclination to despotism. L.S. Vygotsky provided a detailed description of the so-called "seven-star symptoms" of the 3-year-old crisis [2].

Considering the essence of the mental situation on the cutting edge of early and preschool childhood, A.N. Leontyev, points to its defining feature is the discrepancy between the goal of the child's action and its motive, which he considers it the first step towards building the personality [4].

According to D.B. Elkonin, the 3-year-old crisis is associated with new formations within the framework of objective activity that is the emergence of a personal action and the idea of "self" [7]. L.I. Bozovic considers the "the Self-system" to be the core phenomenon of the early age, which includes two inter-related aspects - knowledge about oneself and attitude to oneself and which bring the need for independent actions, the realization and approval of one's own "self",

the degree of realization or deprivation of which determines the course and severity of the 3-year-old crisis symptoms [1].

In their works, E. Erickson and A. Clark stated that the 3-year-old crisis is a peculiar and extremely important period in the development of the child's personality, when the child gains self-confidence and orientation towards social assessment in relations with the social environment [5, 6].

In an experimental study, T.V. Guskova make an insight into the constructive components of a three-year-old crisis and proposes to consider it in two aspects - objective, as a manifestation of a qualitatively new in the child's mental life, and subjective, as a general set of symptoms [3].

Research Methodology. The methodological basis of the research is the concept of the necessity and inevitability of critical periods as stages of mental development arising from the contradictions between the child's mental development and change and his/her environment (L.S. Vygotsky, L.I. Bozhovich, E. Erickson, A. Clark); provisions of P.P. Blonsky about "transitional stages (ages)", which present pedagogical challenges due to the mental instability and the misbalanced, unmotivated behavior of the child; ideas of A.N. Leontyeva, A.V. Zaporozhets, N.A. Menchinskaya on the potential for avoiding the aggravated version of transitional periods and their crisis-free overcoming thanks to the correct organization of the educational process; provisions of L.I. Bozovic about the conditioning of the three-year-old crisis by the deprivation of the child's needs; D.B. Elkonin's works on the determinism of negative manifestations of children during a crisis by the incorrect attitude of an adult to a child, objectively preventing the realization of his/her new abilities; the methodological principle of the analysis of habitual action situations, highlighted by T.V. Guskova for the study of critical ages (stages).

Research methods. To provide for the well-grounded conclusions the authors implemented the following set of methods: theoretical analysis of literature, practical experience analysis, generalization of empirically obtained data, observation, interview, experiment, mathematical methods of data processing.

Results. The purpose of the first stage of the study was to identify the symptoms of a crisis in young children. To provide for the objective diagnosis of the course of three-year-old crisis, first, an interview was held with the pre-school educators, who were asked the following questions: *What changes have occurred in the child's behavior since admission to the pre-school? What is the relationship of the child with adults and children like? How often does he/she demonstrate signs of aggression towards others? In what form? What might be the source of their negativism? What is the intensity of the negative reactions of the child, and what consequences do they have?*

The educators' response analysis showed that the adults believe that negative reactions towards the surrounding adults and children prevail in the behavior of most children when the toddlers enter a preschool or after periods of long absence due to illness, for exam-

ple. In particular, there is an intense desire for independence. All of the interviewed educators claim that the reaction of negativism is more common among active children, mainly boys, in the form of a “struggle for their freedom”.

According to the educators, the source of negative manifestations of a child is the incorrect attitude on the part of the adults in the family. Parents do not consider it necessary to take into account the peculiarities of this stage of the child's development, and the child, in turn, transfers the home experience of communication to other adults. Thus, he/she incorrectly interprets the aspirations of other people to assist rather than to fulfill the task for him/her, to advise rather than to persist, etc. The educators named negativism and self-will as the most frequent manifestations of crisis symptoms.

The symptoms of 3-year-old crisis were determined with the method of inclusive observation of the communication of children with each other, their attitude towards adults, toys in the situations that could be regarded by the child as a threat to his/her freedom and independence.

The analysis of the obtained results was carried after dividing the children into three subgroups, mainly, children who have reached the age of three (up to 37 months old), children under 3 and a half years old (under 42 months old) and children under three years old (from 30 months old).

In the first group, 54% of children demonstrate the symptoms of 3-year-old crisis. Moreover, the symptoms of the crisis are most pronounced in boys, twice as many as in girls. According to the frequency of manifestations, the first place is taken by the symptom of “self-will”, the second – “stubbornness”, the third – “negativism”. We did not reveal in this group the symptoms of “inclination to despotism”, “obstinacy”, “rebellion” and “devaluation”.

In the second group, the total number of children who show some symptoms of the crisis is smaller than in the first group making up 42% of the respondents. Naturally, the symptoms are more often manifested in boys (67% of the respondents). Based on the frequency of manifestations, the symptoms are distributed as follows: negativism, stubbornness, self-will, inclination to despotism, devaluation. Obstinacy and rebellion manifestations are not recorded.

The results of the study of the third sub-group give a different picture than in the previous two groups. The above-mentioned symptoms were diagnosed in 79% of the children under study. Based on the frequency of manifestations, they are ranged as follows: stubbornness, devaluation, self-will, negativism, inclination to despotism. Observance and rebellion are not recorded in the observations. In comparison with the other two groups, in this one we observe higher quantitative indicators of the symptoms of “depreciation” and “inclination to despotism”.

The pronounced symptoms of the crisis were observed in 59% of children, among them “willfulness” was diagnosed in 67%, “stubbornness” - in 63%, “negativism” - in 46%, “inclination to despotism” - in 33%, depreciation - in 29% of the surveyed. At the same time, it should be noted that 41% of children have practically no symptoms of a three-year-old crisis, that is revealed only as rare situational manifestations, which indicates a smooth course of the phenomenon under study, due to two opposite reasons. The positive aspect is the correct interaction of adults with the children during the transition from early to preschool age. On the contrary, the negative reason for the absence of manifestations of the crisis is the result of the suppression of the personality, the child's habit of everything done for him. In this case, the suppression of all attempts at independence in the toddler will inevitably delay or even block his/her development.

Figure 1: Diagnostic results of the targeting of negative manifestations in children.

In the process of the research, we also found that the incorrect upbringing can boost the symptoms of a crisis to preserve persist for up to three and a half years old. Overprotectiveness, depriving children of independence and self-determination leads to the manifestations of “negativism” against adults, their desire to help the child. The prolonged crisis can bear irreversible consequences for the development of the child's personality.

The next stage of the study was focused on determining the direction of negative manifestations in children, the degree of their targeting at adults, other children or toys. The methods of this research included observation, natural experiment. It was recorded who the negative emotions of children were aimed at - adults, who were a direct source of negative emotions, or the transfer to other children and toys was carried out.

In children of the first group, 43% of the recorded cases revealed that negative manifestations were aimed at adults, in 36% - at children, and in 21% - at toys. In the second group, negative manifestations aimed at other children prevailed (43%), in relation to adults - 29%, in other cases (28%) negative emotions were directed at both adults and other children.

In the third group, negative manifestations were noted much more often and, as a rule, were aimed at several objects. In 29% of the recorded cases, negative reactions were directed simultaneously at adults, other children and toys, in 14% - to adults and toys, in 21.5% - to other children and toys, 14% - to toys, 21, 5% for adults. Only in this group did we find negative manifestations aimed at toys.

The purpose of the third stage of our study was to determine whether negative manifestations in children are situational, frequent, or fixed. For this, the frequency of their occurrence and the duration of their course were recorded.

Situational manifestations were found in the first group in 75% of children, in the second - in 67%, in the third - in 49%, frequent - in 25%, 33% and 51%, respectively. No fixed manifestations were diagnosed.

Discussion. In accordance with the purpose of the study, we identified and tested pedagogical conditions that contribute to overcoming negative manifestations in the behavior of three-year-old children in a preschool educational institution. We believe that the most effective way to overcome the negative manifestations of a three-year-old behavior crisis is found within the developing environment aimed at reducing the child's negative reactions and providing a positive emotional background for interaction with adults and peers.

An equally important condition is the timely diagnosis of manifestations of negative behavioral reactions, indicating the presence of the crisis symptoms, in order to reduce their external and internal influence on the development of the child's personality as a whole.

In terms of education and upbringing, a prerequisite is the regular listening to the Russian folk tales and children's fiction; those providing the content close to the child's emotional experience, followed up by a conversation about the actions of the heroes and their influence on the feelings and behavior of other characters.

To relieve the symptoms of the crisis, it is very important to form a positive level of relationships between children, adults and peers by conducting theme interviews and using play methods of interacting with the child in spontaneously arising and specially created situations.

Taking into account the determining influence of the family on both the positive and negative course of the transition period, a prerequisite is the organization of fruitful cooperation with the family to implement the principle of the continuity of the educational process to reduce the negative manifestations of the symptoms of the three-year behavior crisis.

The results of educational activity, organized in accordance with the above mentioned conditions are the following: the child acquires the skills of building relationships with peers and adults based on understanding, trust, respect and cooperation available to him/ her; the child develops a positive “self-conception” as well as the basic awareness of his/her feelings and experiences; the child gains basic problem-solving skills to deal with stressful situations and determines the ways to resolve them independently or with minimal assistance of the part of an adult.

The control stage of the study showed a pronounced positive dynamic of changes in the manifestations of three-year behavior crisis in all groups. The total number of children who had symptoms of the crisis decreased to 29%, among them “willfulness” was diagnosed in 16.6% of the respondents, “stubbornness” - in 29.1%, “negativism” - in 20.8%, “inclination to despotism” - in 12.5%, “depreciation” - in 16.6% of the surveyed. The results show that the number of children with the symptom of “self-will” decreased by 4 times, “stubbornness” – by 2.1 times, “negativism” – by 2.2 times, “inclination to despotism” – by 2.6 times, “depreciation” – by 1.6 times, correspondingly.

Figure 2: Diagnostic results of crisis symptoms in children before and after the experimental work.

The analysis of the results of the orientation of negative manifestations in children of all the three groups showed that the frequency of negative manifestations in children decreased by 3.6, for adults – by 1.7, and for toys – by 2 times, correspondingly. At the same time, situational manifestations decreased by 3.6 times, and frequent ones – by 1.8 times.

Conclusion. Early childhood is a most important stage in human development, where the initial forms of self-awareness arise, new relationships with others are built, the child's position is formed, which will largely affect the development of the personality in the future.

The most common cause of negative behavioral reactions in children of three years old is the incorrect influence on the part of adults who do not want to take into account the child's needs and abilities that change with age and, consequently, hinder the manifestation of independence in children.

The improper upbringing of the child leads to a delay in the manifestation of crisis symptoms, both in the form of direct conflict with adults, and in the form of transferring accumulated negative emotions to other children and toys.

To overcome negative manifestations, to establish emotionally positive relationships with children, play methods of interacting with a child in spontaneously arising and specially created situations, listening to children's fiction providing the content close to the child's emotional experience are crucial.

Though making a deep insight into the problem, our research does not reveal all the ways and forms of overcoming negative behavioral manifestations in children during the three-year-old crisis. In particular, a further study is required for such problems as the secrecy of information about intra-family relations and the peculiarities of the work educators and psychologists provide with parents of young children. The solution of these and other problems will make it possible to optimize the development of the child's personality during the three-year behavior crisis, which will have a positive effect on the subsequent periods of his/ her life.

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